

P: ISSN No. 2394-0344
E: ISSN No. 2455-0817

RNI No. UPBIL/2016/67980

VOL.- X , ISSUE- I April - 2025
Remarking An Analisation

Paddy Straw Utilisation for Power Generation in Punjab : Constraints and Policy Implications

Paper Id : 19948 Submission Date : 2025-04-11 Acceptance Date : 2025-04-21 Publication Date : 2025-04-25
This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.15310775

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/remarking.php#8>

Neeraj Sharma

Professor
Evening Studies-MDRC
Panjab University
Chandigarh, Punjab, India

Ashneek Kaur

Research Scholar
Evening Studies-MDRC
Panjab University
Chandigarh, Punjab, India

Abstract

Efficient management of agricultural residue in North-west region of India is a tedious process due to multiplicity of factors. Punjab is one of the north-western states, struggling with the issue of crop residue management. 1.5 per cent of the total cultivable land in India comes under the region of Punjab. Paddy is one of the major crops being produced in the state and its increased production has led to generation of residue in the form of straw and husk. The agricultural residue is not a waste and can bring multifaceted benefits to the environment and farmers. Paddy residue has a huge potential of biomass energy and can be utilized by biomass power plants to generate electricity. Although, these potential benefits can not be realised due lack of feasible alternatives and awareness. This paper focuses on the complexity of factors leading to crop residue burning by the farmers and methods to manage crop residue. It also assesses the availability of surplus biomass in Punjab. It was found that total surplus residue production in the eight districts was 24.4 lakh ton for the year 2020-21. The surplus residue has potential to generate 300 megawatts of electricity. The use of rice residue and its suitability for power generation can be seen as a solution to manage crop residue efficiently and bring down the incidents of stubble burning in Punjab. There are constraints in the way of efficient processing of residue for power generation. These constraints need to be addressed followed by government policy interventions for successful and sustainable use of agriculture biomass in the state.

Keywords Paddy Straw, Biomass Power Plant, Power Generation, Power Potential, Constraints, Policy Implications, Crop Residue Management, Renewable energy, Bioenergy, Circular economy

Introduction

India is an agro economic nation with huge proportion of land devoted to agricultural activities. According to the Ministry of Agriculture, Government of India (2020), a variety of crops are cultivated across different states and Rice (120 Million tonnes) constitutes the major share of total crop production and makes India the second largest producer of rice in the world after China. The upsurge in the production of rice, wheat and other cereal crops can be attributed to the Green revolution which started in India in the 1960s. These decades (1960-2000) not only saw a change in cropping pattern but also a change in the techniques of harvesting the crops. Harvesting with the help of machines make the entire process fast and time efficient but consequently leads to the generation of a huge amount of residue in the form of husk, straw and bales. India generates 611 Million tonnes (Mt) of crop residue every year and about 25 per cent i.e., 152 Mt (approx.) of this residue is surplus. This surplus residue mainly comprises of sugarcane (41 Mt/year), paddy straw (28 Mt/year), wheat (21 Mt/year), cotton stalk (19 Mt/year) (Cardoen et.al., 2015). The huge generation of crop residue brings the opportunity to reuse the biomass as a resource to produce energy. This paper attempts to evaluate the availability of paddy residue for biomass power plants, keeping in account the conventional uses of the residue. The barriers involved in optimal procurement and usage of paddy residue has also been reviewed in this paper.

P: ISSN No. 2394-0344

RNI No. UPBIL/2016/67980

VOL.- X , ISSUE- I April - 2025
Remarking An Anlisation

E: ISSN No. 2455-0817

Objective of study

This paper focuses on the complexity of factors leading to crop residue burning by the farmers and methods to manage crop residue. It also assesses the availability of surplus biomass in Punjab.

Review of Literature

The conventional use of residue consists of its usage as animal fodder, domestic fuel, packaging material, and use in paper mills. In general, wheat residue is preferred over rice for animal fodder as rice stalks contains more silica content which makes it hard and unfit for cattle. Thus, it is the paddy residue which is burnt at large scale due to its limited conventional use. Open field biomass burning is a common practice world-wide, to clear agricultural land for the next sow. In India, 516 million tones of crop residue was generated and out of it, 116 million tones (Mt) was burnt in the year 2017-18. This led to generation of 176.1 Mt CO₂, 10 Mt of CO, 0.31 Mt CH₄, 0.008 Mt N₂O, 0.151 Mt NH₃, 0.814 Mt NMVOC, 0.453 Mt PM_{2.5} (particulate matter) and 0.936 Mt PM₁₀ (Venkatramanan et al., 2021). Punjab alone produces 23 million tones of rice straw in its fields annually and about 80 per cent of it is wasted by the practice of stubble burning (Kumar, 2015).

This huge availability of crop residue is a renewable potential input in the production of bio-fuel and bio-energy. Punjab has a significant potential of biomass to be utilised in production of energy with an estimated production of 3172 MW power. This is the highest among all the states in India (B. Singh et al., 2021). The generation of electricity by using biomass (paddy straw) is undertaken through various processes namely, co-firing, gasification, anaerobic digestion, incineration and fermentation. In 2014, National Policy on Management of Crop Residue was formulated and one of the strategies of the policy was to promote diversified use of crop residue for various purposes such as charcoal gasification, power generation, production of bio-ethanol and much more. The policy also provides for incentivizing of projects and programs that aim at utilizing crop residue. Biomass power and Cogeneration Programme has been implemented by the Ministry of New and Renewable Energy, Government of India in 2016, for optimal use of country's biomass resource for grid power generation. The present study aims at evaluating the availability of surplus paddy residue in the state of Punjab and its potential for power generation. Other alternative methods to manage paddy residue in the state will also be discussed in the study.

Main Text**2.1 Residue Management Scenario in Punjab**

Punjab is considered as the bread basket of the nation. The total area of the state is 56,362 square kilometres which extends from latitudes 29.30° North to 32.32° North and longitudes 73.55° East to 76.50° East. It shares domestic borders with Jammu and Kashmir in the North, Himachal Pradesh in Northeast, Haryana and Rajasthan in the South, whereas it shares international borders with Pakistan in the West. Punjab experiences a balanced mixture of summer, monsoon and winters which makes the land very fertile and favourable for agriculture. Therefore, agriculture is the main occupation of the state. Despite the negligible proportion of 1.53 per cent in total geographical area of India, its share in the central pool of rice and wheat has been very significant. The share of the state in total rice and wheat production of the country was 21.18 per cent and 30.50 per cent respectively, in 2021-22. The agricultural yield in Punjab was the highest across India for wheat and rice in 2020-21. Share of agriculture and allied sector in the total Gross State Value Added (GSVA) has been 28.94% and provides employment to 25.54 per cent of the workforce in the state (Economic Survey 2022-23). The cropping pattern of the state is dominated by food-grain cultivation especially wheat rice crops. The history behind the current cropping pattern can be attributed to the Green revolution. Among all the Indian states, Punjab was the most suitable for introduction of photo period non-sensitive short-duration varieties of wheat and rice during the Green Revolution. This was due to the better infrastructure, higher level of mechanisation and well developed irrigation facilities available in the state. This shift was required to increase the production of food grains and reduce foreign dependence for the same (Kumar, et al., 2015) (Gupta 2019).

In 2021-22, about 87% of the total cultivated land was used for cultivation of food grains including cereals and pulses. The share of wheat and rice in total cropped area has increased in the state over the years due to assured income in the form of Minimum Support Price provided to the farmers, on these two crops. Therefore, out of the total area of 78.2 lac hectares used for crop production, 40% was used for paddy cultivation and 45% was used for wheat cultivation in 2021-22. The total production of rice was 13991.6 (000 Mt) and that of wheat was 17185 (000 Mt) in 2020-21. The percentage share of cropped area for rice and wheat has increased from 4.8 per cent to 40.2 per cent

and 27.3 per cent to 45.1 per cent respectively (Economic Survey 2022-23). Table 1. depicts the gradual rise in cropped area under different crops from 1960-61 to 2021-22.

Table 1. Crop wise percentage share of Cropped Area

Crops	1960-61	1970-71	1980-81	1990-91	2019-20	2020-21	2021-22(P)
Paddy	4.8%	6.9%	17.5%	26.9%	40.1%	40.2%	40.2%
Wheat	27.3%	40.5%	41.6%	43.6%	45%	45.15%	45.1%
Maize	6.9%	9.8%	5.6%	2.5%	1.5%	1.3%	1.3%
Bajra	2.69%	3.7%	1%	0.2%	0.03%	0.05%	0.0%
Barley	1.4%	1%	0.9%	0.5%	0.12%	0.08%	0.1%
Pulses	19.1%	7.3%	5%	1.9%	0.5%	0.4%	0.8%
Oilseeds	3.9%	5.2%	3.7%	1.5%	0.6%	0.5%	0.6%
Sugarcane	2.8%	2.3%	1%	1.3%	1.2%	1.14%	1.1%
Cotton	9.4%	7%	9.6%	9.3%	3.2%	3.2%	3.2%
Vegetables	1.2%	0.9%	1.1%	0.7%	3.3%	1.4%	1.1%
Fruits	0.6%	0.6%	0.4%	0.8%	1.1%	1.19%	1.2%
Other crops	17.7%	14.8%	12.6%	10.8%	3.6%	5.39%	5.3%

Source: Directorate of Agriculture and Farmers' Welfare, Punjab

This system of production and cropping pattern, however, has shown deteriorating effects on the environment, soil health and ground water levels. The remarkable increase in the production of these crops on one hand made the country self-sufficient but on the other hand led to the generation of huge amount of crop residue. Farming practices for harvesting rice and wheat have been highly mechanised. It is an impact of these practices that huge amount of scattered, root-bound paddy straw is produced in the fields. Rice straw is considered unfit for cattle feed due to high silica content and its removal from the field is a costly labour-intensive exercise. Moreover, the farmers have a shorter window of 10-15 days between harvesting paddy and planting the next crop. Thus, they burn the paddy residue.

Residue burning is a common residue management practice among farmers in the state of Punjab and other states in India. Paddy residue burning has a deteriorating impact on environment. It leads to emission of greenhouse gases contributing to global climate change. In addition to that, it releases aerosol particles, particulate matters and air pollutants which have harmful effect on human health, agricultural land and soil fertility (Jin et al., 2014) (Porichha, et al., 2021).

2.2. Alternative Methods to Manage Crop Residue.

Scientists and agriculturalists have been suggesting various methods to manage and utilize crop residue as a resource. However, there has been limited application of these methods in practice due to lack of awareness, costs and time management. These alternative methods are a sustainable solution to the menace of crop residue burning. This section provides information on four such methods of managing crop residue.

2.2.1. In Situ Incorporation

In this method crop residue is left on the farmland after the harvest. The next sow is done while the residue of previous crop remains on the field. In-situ incorporation of crop residues offers long-term cost savings on labour and equipment. Although, it requires special machines for sowing next crop. There are various benefits of using this technique, such as cooling effect, increased moisture content in soil, source of carbon and protection from soil erosion. On the other hand, there are some negative implications

for example, infestation by microbes, formation of phytotoxins and immobilization of nutrient. This results in a reduction in yield of next crop and thus, warranting use of fertilizers and chemicals to boost the production. It has been suggested by the National Policy for Management of Crop Residue to practice in-situ direct incorporation of crop residue into soils and mulching. These methods not only curbs crop residue burning incidents but also help in preventing degradation of the environment (National Policy of Crop Residue Management, 2014), (Soam et.al., 2017), (Bhuvaneshwari et.al., 2019).

2.2.2.Composting

Composting is a natural process of decomposition of organic matter with the action of micro-organism under controlled conditions. The product prepared from this process enriches the soil with nutrients and organic matter, thus, increasing the fertility of the soil. The physio-chemical and biological profile of the soil is improved. This in turn leads to replacement of agricultural chemicals, fertilizers and pesticides. Crop residue has high organic content which makes it an appropriate source for developing composts (National Policy of Crop residue Management, 2014), (Bhuvaneshwari et.al., 2019).

2.2.3.Bioenergy

The increasing demand for energy and gradual depletion of non-renewable energy sources demands for a shift to reliable and renewable source of energy. Agricultural biomass is a replenishable and sustainable source of energy (Logeswaran et al. 2020). Electricity production from combusting 1 ton of straw reduced 1471 kg CO₂ equivalent, 15 kg SO₂ equivalent and 6.7 kg C₂H₆ equivalents (Soam et al. 2017). A systematic process of rice production and power generation comprises several steps, including superheated steam drying, husking, polishing, torrefaction, steam gasification, and power generation. These steps minimize loss of energy as the recovery combines heat circulation and process integration. Processing 200 tons rice residue per day could generate 3.4 MW of electricity, with a production efficiency of 32% (Darmawan et al. 2018).

Bio power is generated by direct combustion of straw alone (direct firing), or together with another fuel (co-firing) (Jenkins et.al., 1998). Another alternative method to direct combustion is through gasification, in which straw is gasified by air or steam to generate a fuel-gas mixture of N₂, H₂, CO, and CO₂ followed by combustion of fuel-gas mixture to generate electricity.

Bioenergy can also be generated from crop residues via anaerobic digestion to produce biogas mainly CH₄, which is collected and combusted to generate electricity. (Rao et.al., 2010). Punjab being one of the major producer of rice and rice residue can benefit from this technology. It can be viable solution to crop residue burning practice and energy requirement issues of the state.

Methodology

The study consisted of secondary data gathered related to the area cultivated under paddy, production and yield of the crop in eight districts of Punjab. Two models have been employed for assessing the availability of surplus biomass residue from paddy and evaluation of the biomass power potential of the same. The production of crop residue and availability of surplus residue has been calculated for the eight districts, with the help of following model (Hiloidhari et al., 2019)

Analysis

Table 2. Paddy Residue and its characteristics

Crop	Residue	RPR	Residue Availability Factor (F)	LHV (Mj kg ⁻¹)
Rice	Rice Straw	1.5	0.37	15.54

For the purpose of evaluation the potential of paddy residue for power generation the following model has been adapted from Hiloidhari et al., 2019.

The values mentioned in Table 2. have been adapted from Hiloidhari et al., 2014.

3.1.Crop Residue

(Model 1):

$$CRB = \sum_{i=1}^n RPR_{(i,j)} * Y_{(i,j)} * A_{(i,j)} * F_{(i,j)}$$

where,

$CRB_{(j)}$ is crop residue biomass in tonne (t), in jth district; $RPR_{(i,j)}$ is residue production ratio (1.5); $Y_{(i,j)}$ is crop yield in tonnes per hectare; $A_{(i,j)}$ is area under the crop (area under paddy) in hectares (ha); $F_{(i,j)}$ is residue availability factor (0.32) for paddy straw. Here i refers to crop (paddy) and j refers to district.

3.2. Power potential

(Model 2):

$$BP_{CRB(j)} = \frac{CRB_{(j)} * LHV_{(j)}}{T}$$

where,

$BP_{CRB(j)}$ is biomass power potential from crop residue biomass in jth district in MW; η is the net conversion efficiency (fuel to power); $LHV_{(j)}$ is lower heating value of fuel in Mega Joules (MJ) per kg (residue was converted in kilograms for calculation purpose) and represents the power plant operation time in seconds per year. Here power plant operation time is taken as whole year.

3.3. Selection of Districts

According to Punjab Energy Development Agency Report, there are eleven biomass power projects which are commissioned in eight districts of Punjab. These districts are namely: Jalandhar, Hoshiarpur, Ferozepur, Fazilka, Faridkot, Sri Muktsar Sahib, Moga and Mansa. Biomass power plants are working at different capacities in the above mentioned districts. All the eight districts have been included in the study for the evaluation of availability of crop residue biomass and potential of power generation from the residue.

Result and Discussion

4.1 Availability of Residue

The availability of surplus biomass from paddy crop has been assessed with the application of afore mentioned model (Model 1). The data regarding the production, crop yield and area covered under the production of paddy has been taken from Statistical Abstract 2021. The values related to Residue Production Ratio (RPR) and Residue Availability Factor has been discussed in Table 2.

The values of biomass crop residue available in the eight districts of Punjab along with the respective crop yield and area under cultivation of rice in each district has been presented in Table 3. District Moga has the third largest area under rice production and contributes 4.2 lakh tons of paddy residue annually in the form of rice straw which is the highest amongst the selected districts. It is followed by district Ferozepur which has the largest area under rice cultivation amongst the eight selected districts and generates second highest amount of crop residue i.e., 3.9 lakh tons per year.

Table 3. District wise Crop Yield, Area under Rice and Production of Surplus Residue.

Sr. No.	District	Crop Yield (tons ha ⁻¹)	Area (hectares)	Crop Residue (tons)
1.	Jalandhar	4.551	1,75,100	3,82,502
2.	Hoshiarpur	4.151	79,400	1,58,203
3.	Ferozepur	4.348	1,89,300	3,95,077
4.	Fazilka	3.276	1,16,100	1,82,565
5.	Faridkot	4.104	1,16,200	2,28,905
6.	Sri Muktsar Sahib	4.362	1,85,400	3,88,183
7.	Moga	4.877	1,82,900	4,28,162
8.	Mansa	4.758	1,21,400	2,77,258

Source: Author's calculations

Hoshiarpur and Fazilka district are the lowest residue producing districts with annual rice residue production of 1.58 lakh tons and 1.82 lakh tons respectively. These districts generate a total of 24.40 lakh tons of residue, annually, attributed only to rice crop.

4.2. Biomass Power Potential

The power generation potential from the available biomass crop residue has been evaluated with the help of Model 2 as adapted from Hiloidhari et al., 2014. The value of η i.e., net conversion efficiency has been taken as 25 per cent (Mckendry, 2002). Lower heating value of fuel (LHV), Mj kg^{-1} and power plant operation time (T) has been discussed in Table 2. The annual availability of surplus biomass from paddy is 24.4 lakh tons from all the eight districts. The power potential from the available crop residue in the selected districts has been depicted in Table 4. It vividly presents that a total of 300 MW of electric power can be generated from the available paddy straw residue in the selected eight districts, every year. Out of the selected districts district Moga (53 MW) has the highest potential of generation of electricity through paddy straw followed by Ferozepur (49 MW) and Sri Muktsar Sahib (48 MW). Districts Fazilka and Hoshiarpur are the least power generation potential districts with a power potential of 22 MW and 19 MW respectively. It must be noted that values of power generation potential have been evaluated based on selected parameters and may differ with varied techniques of power production and biomass collection methods.

Table 4. District wise Availability of Crop Residue (Rice Straw) and Power Potential.

Sr. No.	District	Crop Residue (tons)	Power Potential (MW)
1.	Jalandhar	3,82,502	47
2.	Hoshiarpur	1,58,203	19
3.	Ferozepur	3,95,077	49
4.	Fazilka	1,82,565	22
5.	Faridkot	2,28,905	28
6.	Sri Muktsar Sahib	3,88,183	48
7.	Moga	4,28,162	53
8.	Mansa	2,77,258	34
Total		24,40,855	300

Source: Author's calculations

However the results reveal that there is a huge availability of surplus biomass from paddy crop in the selected eight districts of Punjab. These districts have a significant potential for power production if this residue is managed and utilized optimally. It can also curb the menace of residue burning and environmental pollution in the state. Moreover, the procurement of paddy residue from farmers at reasonable prices opens the door for additional income to farmers and generation of employment to local labourers in the supply chain and management of residue.

4.3. Barriers and Constraints

There has been an increasing trend to use paddy straw in the form of renewable energy source in the state of Punjab and the rest of India. The effective and economic utilization of paddy residue is limited due to the presence of various constraints. Some such constraints are explained as under:

4.3.1. Small Size of Landholdings

For instance, small and marginal farmers who comprise of more than 70 per cent of the total farmers in India, have inadequate access to specialised farm machinery for efficient harvest of crops and residue management (Directorate of Economics and Statistics 2021). The initial cost involved in the procurement of residue management machinery makes it infeasible for the majority of cultivators to manage crop residue and further utilize it for additional income. Paddy residue burning practice is still preferred amongst the small and marginal landholding farmers due to lesser cost and shorter time duration in this method.

4.3.2. Cost of Labour

The higher cost of collection, handling charges and labour cost makes it infeasible for the cultivators to manage crop residue (Anand et al., 2022). The high cost and hiring charges of equipment, lack of timely availability of required machinery, implements and financial aid pose a bigger problem in the management of crop residue and supply to the biomass power plants.

4.3.3. Lack of Technical Knowledge

There are some technical constraints related to lack of technical know-how about specialised equipment for residue management amongst the cultivators (Singh and Ranguwal, 2022). Therefore, even if the appropriate machinery and equipment is available in the market, the farmer stands helpless to attain benefits from it due to ignorance and lack of adequate knowledge.

4.3.4. Inappropriate Infrastructure

There exists a skewed market infrastructure for the systematic procurement and storage of crop residue. The nature of paddy residue is seasonal and it is available in the months of October and November, therefore, adequate storage facility becomes detrimental for the use of paddy residue for power generation (Kishore et al., 2004). The unavailability of proper storage and procurement facilities pose a hurdle in the usage of paddy residue as a resource for power generation.

4.3.5. Storage Facility

The storage space for paddy residue plays a significant role in its utilisation by the biomass power plants. Paddy residue is bulky and fluffy in nature which requires voluminous space for storage (Sidhu et al., 2015). Approximately 80 hectares of land is required for storing baled straw of 8000 hectares which is about 1 per cent of the cultivated land. Along with this, the storage premises need to be water proof and protected from high wind-speed otherwise, winds may knock-down loose bales of residue. This makes the farmer destroy this useful resource into ash (Kadam et al., 2000).

4.3.6. Distance of Power Plants

The number of such power plants that convert paddy straw into power are limited and are mostly situated at distant location from majority of the farms. This makes the transportation of paddy residue from fields to plant site an expensive process. The distance of biomass power plants from the fields is a significant factor that needs to be addressed, for its usage as a renewable energy source and makes it more cost-effective (Porichha et al., 2021).

Therefore, it becomes significant to decrease the impact of these barriers for appropriate adoption of renewable technologies and generation of power from crop residue. Adequate awareness regarding up to date residue management technologies along with government support in the form of timely subsidies can strengthen the supply chain and processing of residue. Establishment of storage centres at feasible distance and offering reasonable prices for paddy residue and other crop residue can help promote better residue management, thus, infusing greater surplus availability of crop residue for power production.

Policy Implication

Government of India and various state governments have enacted various laws and policies to regulate the burning of crop residue and promote efficient management and

utilisation of crop residue. Strict laws and fines have also been imposed to bring down the incidents of residue burning.

One such significant policy measure taken by the Ministry of Agriculture and Farmer's Welfare, Government of India, is the National Policy for Management of Crop Residue (NPMCR) in 2014. The policy laid down alternative methods to manage crop residue. Some such goals of the policy were:

1. Advancement of farm machinery and industrial sector to develop and promote sustainable management of crop residue.
2. Diversified use of crop residue for various purposes such as charcoal gasification, power generation and production of bio-ethanol.
3. Provide financial aid to farmers for feasible management of crop residue.
4. Creating awareness and training programmes for the farming community.
5. Formulation and implementation of appropriate laws and policies for effective utilisation of crop residue.

The state governments initiated various projects in lieu of the guidelines of NPMCR to develop farm machinery, devise methods to use crop residue and reduce residue burning activities (NPMCR, 2014).

In order to further the use of advanced farm machinery for management of surplus crop residue, Rs. 1152 crores has been sanctioned by Cabinet Committee for Economic Affairs on March 2018. This has been done to curb the pollution level in the NCR region due to crop residue burning but, still states of Haryana and Punjab have witnessed 17 per cent and 50 per cent of rice straw burning respectively (MoAandFW, 2019).

Central Electricity Authority (CEA), Ministry of Renewable Energy (MNRE), Ministry of Petroleum and Natural Gas (MoPNG) have taken initiatives to utilise rice residue for power generation. CEA has estimated an annual power generation of 203 GW of from rice residue as co- firing with coal (CEA, 2019).

State governments have actively been focussing on the sustainable management and usage of crop residue through various schemes, policies and research projects. In Punjab, Punjab Energy Development Agency (PEDA), Punjab State Council for Science and Technology (PSCST), State Department on Environment and Forestry, Punjab Pollution Control Board (PPCB), Punjab Biodiversity Board have been constituted to develop and promote residue management practices and mitigate the effects of pollution from burning of rice straw.

Punjab Energy Development Agency has established straw based power plant in public private mode in the state with a capacity of 330 MW. Till date, 62.5 MW power is been generated from 0.5 Mt of rice residue (Datta et al., 2020).

Punjab Government gave Rs. 2500 per acre to marginal and small farmers who did not practice rice straw burning in 2019–20 (PTI, 2019).

Punjab Agricultural University (PAU), Ludhiana, have been dedicated to the development of farm mechanisation like Happy Seeder Machine for sowing in standing paddy stubbles, straw collectors, baler, tractor operated paddy straw chopper and modern composting techniques managing and using paddy straw.

Different policies measures are in action to convert paddy waste into a useful resource but the practice of paddy straw burning is still a menace. One of the major barrier is the unsuccessful implementation of policies and inefficient distribution of financial aid to the farmers to procure adequate technology to manage crop residue. Therefore, a combined effort by the government, private sector and farming community is required for sustainable crop residue management.

Conclusion

The growing concern towards the environment and sustainable development has brought greater significance to renewable sources of energy production and power generation. The conversion of paddy straw to electricity is a roadmap towards sustainability and circular economy. There are a variety of other crops such as wheat, coarse grains, sugarcane, cotton, etc., that generate large amount of crop residue along with paddy. The optimal utilization of paddy residue has been discussed as a higher proportion of residue generated from paddy crop is set to fire in most of the states including Punjab. The results clearly depict that Punjab has a huge availability of surplus biomass specifically from rice residue. The potential for generating electric power from agricultural residue of rice crop is quiet significant. These results have been assessed for only eight such districts of Punjab where biomass power plants have been established. Consequently, the

availability of surplus paddy residue for power generation in all the districts of Punjab will be much more and provide for economic and environmental benefits to the state if the constraints in the systematic processing of residue are well addressed. Technical and financial support in the form of training and subsidies will encourage the efficient utilization of paddy residue for generation of power.

References

1. Anand, A., Pathak, S., Kumar, V., & Kaushal, P. (2022). Biochar production from crop residues, its characterization and utilization for electricity generation in India. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 368, 133074. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.133074>
2. Chauhan, S. (2012). District wise agriculture biomass resource assessment for power generation: A case study from an Indian state, Punjab. *Biomass and Bioenergy*, 37, 205–212. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biombioe.2011.12.011>
3. Cardoen, D., Joshi, P., Diels, L., Sarma, P. M., & Pant, D. (2015). Agriculture biomass in India: Part 1. Estimation and characterization. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 102, 39–48. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2015.06.003>
4. CEA, 2019. All India installed Capacity of Power Stations Details Available at.
5. Channi, H. K., Singh, M., Brar, Y. S., Dhingra, A., Gupta, S., Singh, H., Kumar, R., & Kaur, S. (2022). Agricultural waste assessment for the optimal power generation in the Ludhiana district, Punjab, India. *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 50, 700–708. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2021.04.481>
6. Datta, A., Emmanuel, M. A., Ram, N. K., & Dhingra, S. (2020). *Crop residue management: solution to achieve better air quality*. New Delhi: TERI, 9.
7. Directorate of Economics and Statistics, 2021. *Agricultural Statistics at a Glance (New Delhi)*
8. Dutta, A., Patra, A., Hazra, K. K., Nath, C. P., Kumar, N., & Rakshit, A. (2022). A state of the art review in crop residue burning in India: previous knowledge, present circumstances and future strategies. *Environmental Challenges*, 100581. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envc.2022.100581>
9. Hiloidhari, M., Baruah, D., Kumari, M., Kumari, S., & Thakur, I. S. (2019). Prospect and potential of biomass power to mitigate climate change: A case study in India. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 220, 931–944. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.02.194>
10. Jenkins, B., Baxter, L. L., Miles Jr, T. R., & Miles, T. R. (1998). Combustion properties of biomass. *Fuel processing technology*, 54(1-3), 17-46. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-3820\(97\)00059-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-3820(97)00059-3)
11. Kadam, K.L., Forrest, L.H., Jacobson, W.A., 2000. Rice straw as a lignocellulosic resource: collection, processing, transportation, and environmental aspects. *Biomass Bioenergy* 18, 369–389. doi:10.1016/S0961-9534(00)00005-2.
12. Kaur, A. (2017). Crop residue in Punjab Agriculture-Status and Constraints. *Journal of Krishi Vigyan*, 5(2), 22. <https://doi.org/10.5958/2349-4433.2017.00005.8>
13. Logeswaran, J., Shamsuddin, A. H., Silitonga, A., & Mahlia, T. (2020). Prospect of using rice straw for power generation: a review. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 27(21), 25956–25969. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-020-09102-7>
14. Milhau, A., & Fallot, A. (2013). Assessing the potentials of agricultural residues for energy: What the CDM experience of India tells us about their availability. *Energy Policy*, 58, 391–402. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2013.03.041>
15. NPMCR 2014. Available online: http://agricoop.nic.in/sites/default/files/NPMCR_1.pdf
16. PTI 2019. According to the Ministry of Earth Sciences' air quality monitor SAFAR, smoke from stubble burning in Punjab and Haryana accounted for 44 per cent of pollution in Delhi on November 1, the highest this year." Details avail15 A. Dutta, A. Patra, K.K. Hazra et al. *Environmental Challenges* 8 (2022) 100581 able at https://www.business-standard.com/article/pti-stories/stubble-burningcontributedsignificantly-todelhi-ncr-s-pollution-this-year-cpcb-membersecy-119111301401_1.html
17. Porichha, G. K., Hu, Y., Rao, K. T. V., & Xu, C. (2021). Crop Residue Management in India: Stubble Burning vs. Other Utilizations including Bioenergy. *Energies*, 14(14), 4281. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14144281>
18. Qiu, H., Sun, L., Xu, X., Cai, Y., & Bai, J. (2014). Potentials of crop residues for commercial energy production in China: A geographic and economic analysis. *Biomass and Bioenergy*, 64, 110–123. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biombioe.2014.03.055>
19. Rao, P. V., Baral, S. S., Dey, R., & Mutnuri, S. (2010). Biogas generation potential by anaerobic digestion for sustainable energy development in India. *Renewable*

P: ISSN No. 2394-0344
E: ISSN No. 2455-0817

RNI No. UPBIL/2016/67980

VOL.- X , ISSUE- I April - 2025
Remarking An Analisation

- and sustainable energy reviews, 14(7), 2086-2094.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2010.03.031>
20. Singh, J. (2017). Management of the agricultural biomass on decentralized basis for producing sustainable power in India. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 142, 3985–4000. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.10.056>
 21. Singh, B., Szamosi, Z., Siménfalvi, Z., & Rosas-Casals, M. (2020). Decentralized biomass for biogas production. Evaluation and potential assessment in Punjab (India). *Energy Reports*, 6, 1702–1714. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egy.2020.06.009>
 22. STATISTICAL ABSTRACT of Punjab (2021), Economic and Statistical Organisation, Department of Planning, Government of Punjab (INDIA). www.esopb.gov.in
 23. Shafie, S. M., H. H. Masjuki, and T. M. I. Mahlia. (2014). "Rice Straw Supply Chain for Electricity Generation in Malaysia: Economical and Environmental Assessment." *Applied Energy* 135:299–308. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2014.08.10>
 24. Singh, Y., and H. S. Sidhu. (2014). "Management of Cereal Crop Residues for Sustainable Rice-Wheat Production System in the Indo-Gangetic Plains of India." *Proceedings of the Indian National Science Academy* 80(1):95–114. [10.16943/ptinsa/2014/v80i1/55089](https://doi.org/10.16943/ptinsa/2014/v80i1/55089)
 25. Sidhu, H.S., Singh, M., Singh, Y., Blackwell, J., Lohan, S.K., Humphreys, E., Jat, M.L., Singh, V., Singh, S., 2015. Development and evaluation of the Turbo Happy Seeder for sowing wheat into heavy rice residues in NW India. *Field Crops Res* 184, 201–212. doi:10.1016/j.fcr.2015.07.025.
 26. Soam, Shveta, Pal Borjesson, Pankaj K. Sharma, Ravi P. Gupta, Deepak K. Tuli, and Ravindra Kumar. (2017). "Life Cycle Assessment of Rice Straw Utilization Practices in India." *Bioresource Technology* 228:89–98. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2016.12.082>
 27. Singh, G., Singh, P., Sodhi, G. P. S., & Tiwari, D. (2020). Adoption status of rice residue management technologies in south western Punjab. *Indian Journal of Extension Education*, 56(3), 76-82. <https://acspublisher.com/journals/index.php/ijee/article/view/4436>
 28. Singh, S., & Ranguwal, S. (2022). Paddy residue management alternatives in Punjab, India: An Economic analysis. *Indian Journal of Ecology*, 49(4), 1556-1560. <https://doi.org/10.55362/IJE/2022/3697>
 29. Wu, C., Huang, H., Zheng, S., & Yin, X. L. (2002). An economic analysis of biomass gasification and power generation in China. *Bioresource Technology*, 83(1), 65–70. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0960-8524\(01\)00116-x](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0960-8524(01)00116-x)